

Open Science Project DMP - Team Atreides - version 1

Version 1

Description

Data Management Plan for the 2023/2024 Open Science Project work - version 1.

Funder

University of Bologna

Grant

Open Science Course

Researchers

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Marzo (orcid:0009-0006-0853-1772), Erica Andreose
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Organizations

University of Bologna, Italy

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Open Science Project DMP - Team Atreides - version 1](#)

Description:

[Data Management Plan for the 2023/2024 Open Science Project work - version 1.](#)

Researchers:

[Leonardo Zilli \(orcid:0009-0007-4127-4875\)](#)

[Salvatore Di Marzo \(orcid:0009-0006-0853-1772\)](#)

[Erica Andreose \(orcid:0009-0003-7124-9639\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Bologna, Italy](#)

Contact: [Erica Andreose](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [University of Bologna](#)

Grants: [Open Science Course](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

[Open Science Project Software - Team Atreides - version 1](#)

[Software suite for the Open Science project - version 1.](#)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

We haven't considered reusing any kind of software because we wanted to develop something ad hoc for this project.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The software used will be a mix of sparql and python to analyse the data from OpenCitations Meta and Iris.

1.1.5 What is its format?

.py, JSON, CSV, XML

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

The size will be in the span of mb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

We will answer these research questions:

1) What is the coverage of the publications available in IRIS, that strictly concern research conducted within the University of Bologna, in OpenCitations Meta?

2) What is the types of

publications that are better covered in OpenCitations Meta? What is the amount of citations (according to OpenCitations Index) the IRIS publications included in OpenCitations Meta are involved in (as citing entity and as cited entity)?

3) How many of these citations come from

and go to publications not included in IRIS, and how many of these citations involves publications in IRIS as both citing and cited entities?

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

The software used will provide users with a view on the extension of the IRIS publications and the ones that cite IRIS inside of OpenCitations Meta.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

Yes

GitHub

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Organizations identifiers

DOI

Crossref

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

Metadata regarding the creators and the description of the software will be available.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

DCAT

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Linked Open Data

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Open Science, software, python

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GitHub

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-atreides-code>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Software for query and analysis of OpenCitations

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The software will be available on the Github Repository of the Open Science Course of the University of Bologna 2023-2034

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024/tree/main?tab=readme-ov-file>

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-atreides-code>

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

All of the results and the software developed will be available on the Github Repository of the Open Science Course of the University of Bologna 2023-2034

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024/tree/main?tab=readme-ov-file>

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-atreides-code>

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The software will be available on Github and there is no intention in the future to delete the Repository for the course.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DCAT

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

None

Euro

Other

Data Analysis and Software Development

There will be no real cost in making the Software since it is all based on Open software and data that is publicly available.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Salvatore Di Marzo (orcid:0009-0006-0853-1772)

b. Erica Andreose (orcid:0009-0003-7124-9639)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

c. Leonardo Zilli (orcid:0009-0007-4127-4875)

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

The software will be available on the Github Repository of the Open Science Course of the University of Bologna 2023-2034

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024/tree/main?tab=readme-ov-file>.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

The only real information will be on the name of the Authors of the publications that will be analysed which are publicly available.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

UNIBO IRIS bibliographic data dump - version 1

This dataset contains several CSV files detailing the bibliographic data of all the publications by UNIBO scholars as stored in IRIS, which is the national platform for storing bibliographic data.

In particular, the dataset is made of eight distinct files:

- "README.txt": this document
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_CON_PERSON.csv": information about the people involved in the publications (authors, editors, etc.)
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_DESCRIPTION.csv": the string of the authors and other related metadata of publications
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_IDENTIFIER.csv": the identifiers (including DOIs) of publications
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_LANGUAGE.csv": the language in which the publication has been written (when applicable)
- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_MASTER_ALL.csv": basic metadata information of publications (title and date of publication)

- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_PUBLISHER.csv": the publishers of publications

- "ODS_L1_IR_ITEM_RELATION.csv": additional metadata related to the context of publications (publication venue, editors, etc.)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

This dataset contains several CSV files detailing the bibliographic data of all the publications by UNIBO scholars as stored in IRIS, which is the national platform for storing bibliographic data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

All the data provided in the .csv files have been made available in CSV format, using ',' (comma) as field delimiter and '"' (double quotes) for text delimiter (when necessary).

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

268,435,456

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To improve a product

The Data collection will be used to analyze the coverage of the information available in the dataset within OpenCitations Meta.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

"The data set consists of the bibliographic metadata of the publications (of various kinds) of the scholars at the University of Bologna. These information has been extracted from the data available in the IRIS platform of the University (<https://cris.unibo.it/>), that implements the Current Research Information System."

DOI: 10.6092/unibo/amsacta/7608

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

The dataset provides useful insights related to the scientific output of the research conducted within the University of Bologna and related metadata.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024-atreides-code>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

10.6092/unibo/amsacta/7608

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

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<http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

Open Science, Data, citations, Publications

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GitHub

<https://github.com/open-sci/2023-2024/tree/main/docs/Atreides>

GitHub is a developer platform that allows developers to create, store, manage and share their code. It uses Git software, providing the distributed version control of Git plus access control, bug tracking, software feature requests, task management, continuous integration, and wikis for every project.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Other

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

UNIBO IRIS bibliographic data dump, dated 14 March 2024

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Data analysis.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinite time.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

DCAT

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

There are references among the provenance dataset and the OpenCitations Meta.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Analyses

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Set up of scientific and technical committee
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use

- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Leonardo Zilli (orcid:0009-0007-4127-4875)

Data Manager

- b. Erica Andreose (orcid:0009-0003-7124-9639)

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Data Manager

- c. Salvatore Di Marzo (orcid:0009-0006-0853-1772)

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Data Manager

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no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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